

**THE NEW TERMINOLOGIES
AND CHALLENGES TO PRESERVE
THE ALBANIAN LANGUAGE'S
ORIGINALITY**
(The Case of the Development of Town
Planning Terminology)

Linguistics

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Abstract

The rapid unification of communication and the world's conquest by technical and scientific English, lead us towards raising some question marks in the role that some countries should play to setting terminologies in various branches. The constant presence of borrowing raises the need to, firstly, control them, to avoid the use of unnecessary foreign words, and secondly, to avoid the generalization of the so-called, international term. Terminology work helps in cleaning and enriching the general lexicon. Town planning terminology is the linguistic material on which this article is based. It aims to analyze the state of foreign words in this terminology, use cases, the accuracy of use and the possibilities to use, instead of borrowing, the Albanian word. The national linguistic policies necessarily collide with the free choice of the terminology and they get in touch with the international liberalization requirements which let aside some concepts as the preservation of the cultural and linguistic identities. The way Albania manages the town planning terminology nowadays has been taken as a reference to reflect how the expressive abilities of the Albanian language are underestimated, thus using borrowings from the English language and establishing speech in the first place, leaving aside the language. We will not deal here with the ability of the Albanian language to express new concepts, as every language has these tools, but prior to creating new terminologies we should notice how these languages are exploited by their native speakers to embrace the new, to describe and to conceive it, and at last to make it part of the respective cultures. The problem lies in the development of the technology. Here we will focus on the description of privileged ways of linguistic enrichment in function of the tradition that every country has to elaborate terminologies. Whichever the selected way, the challenge is to make the necessary and linguistically accurate terminologies available to users, to expand new scientific knowledge. What we find interesting here is to highlight the conflict among the creation of artificial terms with come from their inaccurate translation and the users' need to understand branches' basic concepts. Making available to users the candidate terms which do not respect the linguistic standards, leads to communication inaccuracy. The creation of these terms should follow specific criteria which do not ignore the spontaneous creation of terms but urge the creation of standardized terms. How do we manage to equip technologically underestimated languages so as to accomplish such a challenge? This is one of the main cases which our analyses are based on.

Introduction

Terminology, as a means of expression and reflection of scientific and technical notions is created in direct connection to the development of new branches and in contact with the innovation that the scientific – technical revolution brings nowadays. Terminology development has caused the creation of new terms and also regularly, the alteration or substitution of already existing terms. When the term is created linguistically accurate, it helps memorizing the notion far more easily, that's why the terminology problems gain a more particular importance in this process. The vocabulary fund continues to expand mainly by terms which have been recently created or the evaluation of already existing terms¹. In 1980, in Albania they created the "Commission for the organization of the work to clear and enrich the Albanian language". Not aimlessly, this commission was raised so as to study the language mainly in the avoidance viewpoint, the harmful foreign influence and the increasing opportunities to express our language, thus continuously enriching its lexicon with words from the popular source or recently created.

¹"The increase of the specific weigh of terminology in the general lexicon constitutes an important distinctive feature of the Albanian language after the Liberation", Kostallari, Androkli. The basic principles of compiling "Today's Albanian language dictionary". SF, nr.2, Tirane, 1968.

In this respect, they have worked even while attempting to achieve a terminology dictionary in the town planning branch. In Albania, this branch has had a development which until the 80's has been closely linked to the development of close branches like architecture and construction. Later on, it evolved as a necessity to expand and well – organize towns. Today town planning stands as an independent study branch, with a consolidated terminology and in continuous contact with the developments abroad.

Work to elaborate this branch's terminology has passed through some stages. Term gathering is made in view of the state of this terminology today and avoiding mainly that part of the terminology lexicon which deals with borrowings and international words. In the work of normalizing terminology, one of the problems is getting the most appropriate Albanian equivalent of the foreign terms. According to particular criteria to elaborate the terminology dictionaries of more than thirty different branches in the Albanian language, there has been translated into Albanian a whole fund of foreign terms which has cleared and enriched the Albanian language. Even during the process of equalizing, coordinating and translating in particular the terminology of town planning, we have preserved the same criteria, which aim to explore the new borrowings and the difference among old borrowings which are embedded in our language. There have been attempts to avoid or limit the use of some borrowings from European languages and they have been objective to international words. Generally, the issues of translating the terminology into the Albanian language have been previously noticed are occasionally are still noticed until recently within that circle of broad problematic in which all the Albanian lexicon is treated. This has brought the analyses of most terminology translation issues from a broader prospective and not closely linked to the specific particularities of this special lexicon, which serves to express scientific – technical concepts and to differentiate them from one – another with fixed and clearly established boundaries. Terms should be as simple and understandable as possible so they can be acquired by a broad mass of users but often, borrowings from foreign languages do not express anything about the content of the term, about the one that does not know the language of origin². The problem of the presence of foreign terms in town planning terminology has been previously discussed noticing the state, the cases of the use, accuracy of use and opportunities of using the Albanian equivalent instead of the borrowings. The analyses of this state is based on the reflection of the term's life in the Albanian language dictionaries throughout the years, in the town planning texts as school subjects, in laws and regulations which explain and put this branch to practice, and also in some periodic editions which treat this branch's problems. Foreign terms have been analyzed divided into two groups, foreign terms expanded internationally and secondly, terms which are not internationally expanded. In his article about international words in the Albanian language, JosifKole claims that the quality of internationality is relative because with international phenomena we understand those which are widespread in some or more places, people, etc. so even when we talk about international words, we know they are present in some languages³. Linguists' most common thought is that we can discuss words' internationality only when they are

²Leka, Ferdinand. Guide to elaborating the scientific – technical terminology. Tirane, 1983.

³Kole, Josif. About international phrases in Albanian. SF 1984/3, Tirane.

encountered in similar form or meaning in some languages which do not belong to the same family and which represent two or more such groups or language families.

I. Diachronic point of view

While elaborating town planning terminology, we notice a foreign group of terms which are closely linked to the history of cities' development throughout the centuries. These terms belong to the town planning history as a study branch and present the reality of ancient civilizations. As in terminology, we often discuss the case of accurate communication, there arises the case of translating these terms as well as all other borrowings into Albanian. In this viewpoint we encounter the need of making a diachronic categorization of borrowings in function of the stages of this branch's development as a science in itself. This is relatively simple for the town planning branch as we clearly notice the pre-industrialization period and the industrialization period and thereafter. The last one marks even the first theoretical editions of the branch⁴. The terms, which will characterize the first period, are directly linked to the historical towns and town art. As a consequence, even their origin is from old Latin or Greek. Although today these terms are not part of the Albanian language dictionary (this is linked even to the fact that only a limited number of terms becomes part of a non – terminology dictionary), they are part of town planning school books in Albanian. For this group of terms, there is no permanent attitude has been maintained as their presence in the Albanian language is early and it would be difficult to substitute it with an Albanian term because of the term's embedding and its not frequent use. The need to use these terms is limited even for the fact that the town planning branch in itself has developed, thus bringing a lot of other terms which express new concepts in this branch. In this group of terms borrowed from the Albanian language, we can mention: *agorëgreke*, *akropol*, *bulefter*, *bazilikë*, *domus*, *insula*, *aksplanadë*, *ekstedër*, *forum romak*, *kondominium*, *kotexh*, *odeon*, *pilastër*, *stojë*, *platonë*, *tempull*, etc. These terms mainly express types of buildings according to their construction particularities and blocks of buildings according to their functions established for the time.

II. Albanian equivalent alongside the foreign term

In different periods of time, the care to enrich the Albanian language has had its own particularities but mostly recently, we notice a stream of borrowings which have substituted terms or components of the terminology phrase. In most studies, foreign words borrowings arise naturally. The foreign term is seen as a complementary source to enrich the language and because of this, A. Xhuvani claims: "No language can stop other languages' influence and be pure from anything foreign"⁵. Analyzed from their qualities, borrowings are international terms and non-international foreign terms. To establish international terms, various ideas have been expressed, but the principle followed to make about 35 Albanian – foreign language terminology dictionaries

⁴ Beaudet, Gérard. Naissance et développement de l'urbanisme : jalons In : Profession urbaniste. Montréal : Presses de l'Université de Montréal, 2007. Internet: <<http://books.openedition.org/pum/280>>.

⁵ Xhuvani, Aleksandër. Purity of Language, New Letters, VIII, 1950.

has been the one expressed in Today's Albanian language dictionary where the term "internationalphrase" is defined as "word or expression of the same origin and similar form which is found in many languages of the world". A. Kostallari in "Basic principles for elaborating Today's Albanian language Dictionary states:"... these words of the international lexicon belong to all people ..."⁶. By analyzing the town planning terminology according to this criterion and by considering the terms 'phonetical and graphic adaptability, we notice that in this terminology there is a number of terms where one of the component parts of the terminology phrase or the whole phrase is an international term. We can mention terms like: *aglomeracion urban*, *planifikim urban*, *akskompozimi*, *aktiviteturbanistik*, *ansambëlurbanistikompakt*, *celulëbanimi*, *distancëoptimale*, *fizionomiurbanistike*, *kompleksndërtimor*, *infrastrukturë urbane*, *instrument iplanifikimit*, *planiorientuar*, *lokalizimindërtimit*, *panoramë (e qytetit)*, *periferi (e qytetit)*, *potencialpërurbanizim*, *rinovim urban*, *(rrjet) interurban*, *transformim urban*, *koncentrim (iqytetit)*, *ansambëlurbanistik*, etc.

The extent of using these terms and absorbing them is different because there are a lot of factors which influence on them. Though they are international terms, they have a wide extent in general, while elaborating terminology in Albanian and its codification in dictionaries, we aim to give the Albanian equivalent of the terms as this helps even in the clarification and enrichment of the general lexicon⁷. Finding the Albanian equivalent is the main task throughout this process even because of the fact that above all we aim to the accuracy of the concept. Using a foreign term requires a good knowledge of the concept in the foreign language so as we can know whether the term adopted in Albanian fully or partially complies in meaning and if it creates the same connections with other terms. Here we have the example of the adjective term "urban". In most terminology phrases where this adjective is present, the meaning of the term is closely linked to the *town/city* as an administrative unit. Here we can mention terms like: *element ipërherëshëm urban*, *element ipërkohëshëm urban*, *formë urbane*, *hapësirë urbane*, *mobilitim urban*, *model urban*, *nyjë urbane*, *organizimihapësirës urbane*, *përmirësim urban*, *modelim urban*, etc. Whereas in other phrases it refers only to an inhabited area, in the town or country, for example the terms: *qendër urbane*, *hapësira urbane tëgërshetuara*, *territor urban*, *njësi urbane*, *zonë urbane*, etc. This term, in a foreign language, also refers to an inhabited area, apart from the first meaning related to the town, but this inhabited area is characterised by a vast number of buildings and a certain number of populations.

Obviously, these cases bring confusion in terminology, that's why we tend to avoid them while working to elaborate terminology.

The cases when the Albanian equivalent is used alongside the foreign term are frequent but this shows a tendency that the speakers of small countries have to use words of foreign origin, thus pointing out their recognition by a broader pseudo – intellectual world. For these cases of borrowings while working to make a possible dictionary of the town planning branch, there's been

⁶ Kostallari, Androkli. The basic principles of compiling "Today's Albanian language dictionary", SF, 1968/2.

⁷ Pasho, Hëna. Linguistic problems of terminology in the Albanian language, Albanological Editions, Tirane, 2017.

maintained a permanent attitude by putting in the dictionary only the Albanian term which is mostly used and widely known, but its use is limited because of the use of the term in the foreign language. The codification of these terms in the terminology dictionary makes their value increase and normalize.

III. Restriction of international technical terms

Terms, the internationality of which is limited, make another category. In the cases when the term has had the same form or content just in two or three languages of the same family, or just in two language families, there have been attempts to specify the concept and to substitute the term with an Albanian word. As a source for the term in the Albanian language we have used the general lexicon, the dialect lexicon and terms from other branches which have expanded their meaning, becoming part of new terminology phrases because of their use in a new branch. In this group of terms, we have included even those cases when only the foreign prefix or suffix needed to be translated into Albanian. So we have from: *ambient urban - mjedis urban, deformimiterritorit - shformimiterritorit, densifikimiterritorit- dendësimiterritorit, disurbanizim - çurbanizim, hapësirë urbane komplekse - hapësirë urbane e ndërlikuar, menaxhim urban - gjerim urban, ndërtimkaotik - ndërtimirrëmujshtëm, rritjekoncentrike e qytetit-rritjebashkëqendrore e qytetit, zonë e konsoliduar - zonë e qëndrueshme, strukturëcentrike - strukturëqendrore, koordinimiplanit -bashkërendimiplanit, zonifikimiterritorit - zonimiterritorit, reabilitim urban - riaftesim urban, kapacitetmbajtësiterritorit - nxënësi e territorit, formë urbane konstelacion - formë urbane yjësore, etj.*

We have translated into Albanian even those borrowings which have brought new concepts of the branch which we have no Albanian term in use for yet. These terms have accompanied the concepts, but the clarity is still limited in the close circle of the specialists who have often misused foreign terms. So that the term is accurate and is widely extended, there have been proposed candidate terms sometimes formed by the translation of the word and sometimes formed with the Albanian language tools. The fate of these candidate terms can not be preceded, but the work done to provide the Albanian equivalent of the terms in many branches throughout the years has shown us that the user should have the right means of communication so that this last one can be more accurate and direct.

Conclusion

After a rigorous study of the town planning terminology we conclude that international terms, perceived from the language and which do not have other competitive terms to express the same concepts, belong to that borrowings sphere which is called necessary and as a consequence they play a good role in creating this terminology. Other borrowings which for a certain period of time have met a need, have been substituted or will be gradually substitutes with the Albanian word. Following the elaboration of the town planning terminology, the further finding of the Albanian equivalent plays an important part. The Albanian equivalents help acquiring the branch's knowledge more quickly. They should respect the nature of the Albanian language and express

accurately the content of the foreign term. As the researcher HënaPasho claims “Borrowings is not just a mechanical passage from one language to the other, but it is the process of organic acquiring of the lexemes and word formation elements and the meaning suitability in the Albanian language”⁸. Early attempts to find the Albanian equivalent of borrowings show that there is a tendency to construct the term based on the Albanian language or to use the word of the general or dialectic lexicon raising it at the level of a term.

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